

Selecting Locations for Avionics Antennas: A Structured Approach

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Abstract. Designing installations for avionics antennas (communications, navigation, identification friend or foe, or electronic warfare receivers and jammers) involves compromises among many sometimes conflicting requirements. The antennas must not only transmit or receive well enough to meet the requirements of their associated avionics systems, but must simultaneously meet aircraft-specific constraints. For example, aircraft performance factors might limit space for antenna installations for aerodynamic, structural, environmental, or electromagnetic compatibility reasons. This paper describes a methodology that analytically estimates an avionics system's performance when its antennas are installed at various compromised locations. The methodology begins with a computer-aided design analysis to determine what aircraft structure lies in the antenna's free-space field of view from a given installed location. Because electromagnetic waves cannot propagate through electrical conductors, this first step allows candidate locations to be eliminated if the aircraft blocks too much of the antenna's field of interest. Once a location is identified that provides a sufficiently unobstructed field of view, the geometric theory of diffraction or other appropriate electromagnetic scattering code is used to obtain a more detailed prediction of the installed antenna's performance. Then, an analysis of the avionics system performance is made to determine whether the installed device can meet avionics system requirements. When antenna locations are found that simultaneously satisfy avionics system requirements and meet other constraints, prototype testing can be accomplished to verify that predicted antenna patterns. The proposed methodology is a "top-down" approach to determining antenna locations that applies flexible analytic techniques early in the design process to "filter out" unfeasible approaches and significantly reduces the number of "design, build, and test" iterations needed to achieve a successful system.

Definitions and Background.

Field of View: The region of space around an antenna from which the antenna can detect or into which the antenna can radiate electromagnetic energy.

Field of Interest: The region of space for which an antenna is the primary detector or source of electromagnetic radiation.

Relating Field of Interest and Antenna Field of View. The field of interest can be larger or smaller than the field of view for a given antenna installation. If the antenna's field of view is smaller than the field of interest, the antenna can be designed to scan the field of interest, or multiple antennas can be installed to cover the field of interest using the sum of the various antennas' fields of view. If the antenna's field of view is larger than the field of interest, there could be overlap between adjacent antennas that may or may not be desirable. Overlapping coverage may be desirable since it allows comparison in adjacent antennas' amplitudes to make angle of arrival (AOA) determination (1:60). Undesirable overlap can be eliminated by constructing an iris limiting the antenna's field of view to the desired field of interest.

Introduction. This paper outlines and demonstrates a structured approach to selecting locations for avionics antennas. As "electromagnetic eyes and ears," an aircraft's various antennas are important factors in overall mission effectiveness (2:Ch 3, 3-9). All avionics devices that transmit or receive (such as communications, navigation, identification of friend or foe [CNI]; radar; and electronic warfare [EW] equipment) rely on some form of antenna system to interface on-board transmitters and receivers to the outside world. To perform satisfactorily, avionics systems' antennas must meet gain and field of view requirements. Gain specifies how well an antenna can convert radiation incident from a given direction into signal power for a receiver or, reciprocally, how well an antenna converts signal power from a transmitter into radiation in a given direction. Some antennas (such as for air traffic control radio communications) are intended to be omnidirectional, having a full 360° field of view and equal gain in all directions. Other antennas (such as for satellite communications, radar, instrument landing, and direction-finding systems) are intended to be directional, and have an assigned, limited field of interest and directional gain. Antennas selected for installation must have sufficient gain and field of view to meet the avionics system's requirements. Free space antenna

patterns are measured with the antenna removed from any other electromagnetic scatterers to determine the antenna's inherent gain and field of view characteristics. For effective operation, the antenna must be installed on the aircraft at a location that results in acceptable "installed antenna patterns". Installed antenna patterns are measured with the antenna mounted on the aircraft to show the effects of the aircraft (which is, among other things, an electromagnetic scatterer) on the antenna's radiation characteristics. An effective antenna installation must take the aircraft scattering effects into account. Often, however, the obvious electromagnetically "optimum" location for an antenna cannot be used due to other constraining factors (such as vibration, severe environment, the presence of other aeronautical equipment such as avionics sensors, or adverse aerodynamic effects the antenna would cause). Therefore, antenna locations are usually compromises between electromagnetic performance and other constraining factors. The process of optimizing antenna locations can be improved by using an organized method of evaluating design alternatives. This paper describes a method of systematically assessing compromise antenna locations to facilitate selection of the "best" available location. If applied early enough in the aircraft development process, the methodology can identify unavoidable shortfalls in antenna performance early, allowing further design work to be initiated as necessary to compensate for the shortfalls.

Design Methodology. The proposed methodology consists of four distinct steps. Step 1 is a computer-aided design (CAD) analysis to determine what aircraft structure lies in the antenna's field of view when the antenna is installed at a particular location and with given boresight azimuth and elevation angles. Once a location is identified that provides a sufficient unobstructed field of view, Step 2 uses an appropriate electromagnetic scattering model to obtain a more detailed prediction of the installed antenna's performance (i.e. installed antenna patterns). Step 3 consists of using the predicted antenna patterns to analyze the avionics system performance to determine whether the installation design can meet avionics system requirements. For sensors (such as missile warning receivers) that detect non-coherent radiation in the electro-optic region, Step 3 can be omitted because the CAD analysis result itself is an accurate model of the geometric optic nature of propagation at extremely short wavelengths. When antenna locations are found that simultaneously satisfy avionics system requirements and meet other constraints, prototype testing can be accomplished as Step 4 to verify that the predicted antenna patterns are accurate. The details of the recommended methodology can best be described by demonstrating how it applies to a sample problem.

Sample Installation Problem. For purposes of illustration, consider the design task of installing a radar warning receiver (RWR) on a hypothetical aircraft. The RWR will have four antennas, each of which will cover 90° in azimuth. RWR specifications require each antenna's field of interest to cover $\pm 45^\circ$ in azimuth and elevation. The sample design problem is limited to the antenna that

provides coverage in azimuth from the nose to the "3 o'clock" position (90°). RWR specifications require the antenna to have gain of not less than -6 dB_i (decibels referenced to an isotropic antenna) at 9.0 GHz throughout its field of interest. Free-space tests of the antenna to be installed (a 2.5 inch cavity-backed spiral antenna) show that it has a conical field of view with a 60° half angle (centered on the antenna boresight) with a maximum gain (on the antenna's boresight) of 0 dB_i and adequate gain $\pm 45^\circ$ from boresight to meet the requirements for gain in the specified field of interest. These antenna characteristics indicate that the antenna should be mounted so its boresight is at 45° azimuth and parallel to the horizon. From an analysis of aerodynamic and performance factors, four candidate antenna locations are available. The aircraft and antenna locations are illustrated in Figure 1.

Step 1: Computer-Aided Design Analysis of Antenna Field of View. In this step, the aircraft geometry is examined from the perspective of an observer situated at the proposed antenna location. The observer is restricted to "seeing" only regions of space and any obstructions that are within the antenna's field of view. Referring to Figure 2, a coordinate system is chosen that represents the "pilot's eye" view from the cockpit. Azimuth angles are measured from the nose (which is 0° azimuth) clockwise as viewed from above the aircraft. Elevation angles are referenced to the horizontal plane that contains the aircraft's nose and wings. This horizontal plane is 0° elevation. Positive elevation angles are measured above, and negative elevation angles are measured below the horizon. A picture of the field of view as seen from the antenna location is projected onto a sphere defined in the reference coordinate system with a radius that represents a "large distance" from the aircraft. The spherical projection of the picture of the antenna's field of view is then transformed using Mercator projection into rectangular coordinates. Mercator projection transforms the projected picture so that each unit increment of azimuth angle occupies the same dimension regardless of the value of the elevation angle. This transformation results in a distortion of the physical dimensions of the projected picture similar to the elongation of the continent of Antarctica evident in Mercator projections of the earth's surface. Figure 3 shows the symbology used in this paper to denote the boresight angle of the antenna and the roughly circular limit to the antenna's field of view. Darkened areas indicate regions of the antenna's field of view that are obstructed by the aircraft. These obstructions are important for two reasons. First, an obstruction in the antenna's field of interest would most likely reduce gain in the obstructed region because electromagnetic waves will not propagate through the aircraft structure (which is usually an electrical conductor). Secondly, all obstructions within the antenna's field of view are potential paths for electromagnetic reflections, which could distort the antenna pattern due to constructive and destructive interference between the direct free-space path and reflection paths between the antenna and a point in space. Figure 4 shows the results of CAD analysis of the fields of view for the four proposed in-

Figure 1. Aircraft Geometry and Antenna Locations for Sample Problem

Figure 2. Coordinate System for Computer-Aided Design and Installed Antenna Pattern Plots

stallation locations. Plots for Locations 1 and 4 clearly show that much of the region below the aircraft is obstructed, so there is no reason to expect successful performance from

either location. For example, no direct free-space path exists between the RWR antenna and a threat a 0° azimuth and -15° elevation for either Location 1 or 4. To sense a

Figure 3. Display Symbology for CAD Analysis

threat in this region, the RWR antenna has energy available only from secondary scattering effects (such as surface dif-

fraction around the fuselage and other diffractions from other scattering locations). Since the magnitudes of secondary scattering components are generally significantly lower than any existing direct component, gain at 0° azimuth and -15° elevation would probably be much lower than that specified for this RWR antenna. Locations 2 and 3 both have an unobstructed field of interest, but the antenna pattern for Location 3 could be distorted by interference due to reflections from the side of the fuselage obstructing the antenna's field of view from 0° to -15° azimuth near the horizontal plane (0° elevation). As a filter, then, the initial step of CAD analysis has narrowed our further analysis to Locations 2 and 3. The next step in the analysis has been carried out for Location 1 as well to demonstrate its poor performance as predicted by the electromagnetic scattering model.

Figure 4. Plots of CAD Field of View Analysis Results

Step 2: Electromagnetic Modeling of Installed Antenna Patterns. This step involves the use of a computerized electromagnetic scattering model applicable to the aircraft geometry and frequency of interest. In this case, the aircraft dimensions are "large" with respect to the wavelength of the frequency of interest (the free-space wavelength at 9 GHz is about 1.3 inches). For such a scattering

problem (referred to as a "high frequency" problem), either the Geometric Theory of Diffraction (GTD) or the Physical Theory of Diffraction (PTD) can be used (3:570-850). GTD is selected for this demonstration because of the availability and success of the Near-Zone Electromagnetic Code, Basic Scattering Code (NECBSC) (4:298-301). To use NECBSC, the user must describe the aircraft as a collection of canoni-

cal shapes (cylinders, ellipsoids, cone frustra, and flat plates). Careful analysis of the aircraft geometry and the antenna field of view can usually result in a satisfactory aircraft model based on a few simple shapes. The cavity-backed spiral antenna model developed elsewhere (5:34-41), the plot geometry desired, and the aircraft model are the only inputs required by the NECBSC model. For this analysis, the coordinate system and display described in Figures 2 and 3 for the CAD analysis plots is also used for the predicted antenna pattern outputs. Plots of results for vertical polarization for Locations 1, 2, and 3 are shown in Figure 5. The plot for Location 1 is included to demonstrate the effects of unacceptable blockage on the antenna pattern. In the plot for Location 1, the severe reduction in gain caused by aircraft blockage at negative elevations can be seen (in fact, the outline of the aircraft can be seen in the antenna pattern plot). Also, the adverse effects of interference caused by reflections can be seen as reduced gain at certain positive elevation angles. The plot for Location 2 shows the installed antenna performance is a virtually undistorted spiral antenna pattern. Appreciable gain is realized throughout the antenna's field of view, and the coverage in the field of interest meets or exceeds RWR system requirements. The plot for Location 3 clearly shows the adverse effects reflections from the side of the fuselage have on antenna gain in the field of interest.

Step 3: Assessing Avionics System Performance Using Predicted Installed Antenna Patterns. In our example problem, Location 2 or 3 could be used for the installation depending on specific aircraft mission requirements. Location 2 meets all performance characteristics specified for the antenna system and would therefore be the "best" location based on electromagnetic performance. However, there could be complications (such as the length of cable required to connect the antenna and the problem of routing the cable around fuel tanks and other internal wing components) in selecting Location 2. Trading off the superior electromagnetic performance of Location 2 for the simpler installation at Location 3 could be feasible. For Location 3, there are regions where antenna performance falls below RWR specifications. The decision as to whether Location 3 performance shortfalls can be tolerated by the RWR should be based on aircraft mission requirements. The plots in Figure 5 have been calibrated in relative free space detection range capability by applying the Friis Transmission Equation (6:63-65). This calibration allows assessment of how much detection range performance degradation results from selecting Location 3 and where the degradation occurs. In this instance, the degradation of detection range falls in a relatively small cone off the aircraft nose. If the aircraft's mission could tolerate this degradation, Location 3 could be selected for the antenna installation over Location 2. If the antenna is also to be used for determining the angle of arrival (AOA) of the detected signal, further analysis of antenna performance must be accomplished. To achieve this, antenna patterns for the other 3 RWR antennas (those covering the remaining 270° azimuth) would need to be generated. Then a model of the RWR's AOA

estimation algorithm (7:97-100) could be used to determine how well each design meets RWR requirements for AOA determination. A final decision on which design to implement must be based on RWR performance in all relevant categories and the actual mission requirements of the aircraft.

Step 4: Antenna Pattern Testing. The final step in the proposed methodology is measurement of the installed antenna patterns. Given the current and projected state of the art, computer modeling of antenna patterns complements—rather than substitutes for—antenna pattern testing (5:80-86). Testing is necessary to verify the computer model results (which, in this demonstration, have omitted some far-field scattering effects which may influence the actual antenna pattern). Verification is essential to ensure that acceptable performance can be achieved before costly integration of the actual antenna on the aircraft is begun. Because the initial set of candidates has been reduced from four to one or (at most) two locations, antenna pattern measurement efforts can be focused on installation designs that have a high probability of meeting RWR performance requirements. The reduction in the number of tested installation configurations allows the design of prototype hardware to be optimized for the locations chosen for testing. Also, the reduced number of configurations allows other efficiencies that can improve the quality and timeliness of the final measured antenna pattern data.

Summary. The proposed methodology proceeds from the top down. At the beginning of the design process, a number of candidate installation locations are proposed based on the antennas' electromagnetic performance and other considerations. A simple geometric analysis is then used to eliminate installation locations that are clearly unacceptable from the viewpoint of the field of interest required for the antenna. Higher-power analytic tools in the form of electromagnetic scattering codes are next used to predict installed antenna patterns for the locations that pass initial screening. Predicted antenna patterns are then used to assess any differences between the performance specified for and achieved by the antennas. The availability of quantified antenna performance data allows design tradeoffs to be made based on the actual aircraft mission and other factors. The methodology ends with actual prototype testing of designs that pass the screening accomplished using analytical tools. Test assets are concentrated on designs that have a high probability of meeting user requirements. The methodology is currently used by the Aeronautical Systems Division to analyze conceptual aircraft designs and to assist system program offices in retrofitting EW sensors on existing aircraft

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Figure 5. Predicted Antenna Patterns for 9.0 GHz, Vertical Polarization

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